

THE METHODOLOGICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF THE PROBLEM OF TRAINING THE TEACHER-PSYCHOLOGIST TO PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY

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Abstract. This paper about the approach aimed at preparing the students of the faculty of higher education, pedagogy and psychology for the profession develops the aptitude for effective professional activity, develops and strengthens the important professional qualities, and prepares the graduate for practical professional activity.

Key words: communicative-technological; individual, formation, personnel management, approach.

ТЕКСТ НАУЧНОЙ РАБОТЫ НА ТЕМУ «МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЕ И МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ПОДГОТОВКИ ПЕДАГОГА-ПСИХОЛОГА К ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ»

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается подход, направленный на подготовку студентов факультета педагогики и психологии к профессии, развивающий способность к эффективной профессиональной деятельности, развивающий и укрепляющий важные профессиональные качества, подготавливающий выпускника к практической профессиональной деятельности.

Ключевые слова: коммуникативно-технологический; индивидуальный, формирование, управление персоналом, подход.

Based on the modern approach in psychology, development of the humanization trend, innovation, technological development of education and training, the field of theoretical and practical training of the student is growing in accordance with the axiological approach to professional activity. The psychological approach is becoming the basis of a creative approach to the activity of a pedagogue-psychologist.

As the analysis of training manuals on pedagogical and psychological science shows, it is possible to increase the number of shortcomings with the existing opportunities for professional training. As it was mentioned above, the reason for finding a holistic concept of future professional activity is the imbalance of the curriculum, pedagogical and psychological framework, the "inconsistency" of the main curriculum, the weak connection of innovation to the educational curriculum, and the lack of integration in the teaching of psychological and pedagogical science. The focus on top specialization does not reflect the level of understanding of individual social protection in previous decades. At present, only a well-educated person, who adapts the direction and content of his activity to technological change or to the needs of society, can be truly socially protected. One of the top professional training in the field will gradually pass from the educational system to development and other professional activities.

The educational system is poorly focused on the interrelationship between higher educational institutions and the actual demand for knowledge and skills in modern society.

Studying the problem made it possible to identify a serious conflict in the training of a pedagogue-psychologist. The most important of Institutes is as follows:

- the abstract program (knowledge) of the educational activity and the real program of the future pedagogical activity, where the success of the practical psychological-pedagogical activity is not guaranteed;
- based on previous experience, based on personal perception and real professional literate behavior;
- information and the opportunity to acquire personal training in the field of training;
- personal and professional motivation for successful activity.

Motivational attitude is undoubtedly one of the most important problems in the problem of creating a specialist. As mentioned above, the main components of a unique pedagogical activity are:

- Motivational;
- Content-active;
- Intellectual;
- Communicative and technological;
- Result-practical;
- Assessment is prognostic.

The collection of specific knowledge in pedagogical activities is included in the technological component of professional development and is determined by knowledge of the theory, methodology and technology of the Japanese language learning, as well as the presence of a qualification formed in the field of education.

The main multiplier of the technological component of learning is awareness, flexibility, mobility, adequacy, creativity, independence, accuracy of pedagogical behavior, communication serves.

Studying the problem of student motivation, analysis of pedagogical literature allows to form the main direction of improvement of student practical motivation:

1. The leading task of teaching in pedagogical higher education institutes should be to develop creative abilities of pedagogues and psychologists.

2. For this purpose, it is necessary to provide a great differentiation and individualization of the content and organization of practice (taking into account the professional orientation of the task offered to the student, general education professional training, individual characteristics, selective selection of the object of work and activity group, collective, group and individual work form) comprehensive).

3. The practice should be directly connected with the study of the subjects in the psychological-pedagogical framework, for this purpose, it is necessary to consider the integrative courses, which ensures the proper connection of the theoretical knowledge (formed in the sphere of the subjects) with the actual practical activity. In such an organization of training, the enrichment of the theoretical basis for the organization of independent practical activities from the third cup is ensured.

4. The student's system of acquiring pedagogical technology.

5. It is important that teaching in higher educational institutions provides for the existence of a form of transition from theoretical teaching to direct practice. Today, at the base of the faculty of pedagogy and psychology, one of such forms is multi-methodological camp.

As a psychological-pedagogical framework system for the development of students' personality, the following is the basis:

- General and methodological training of the specialist;
- Practically oriented technology that allows integration of new knowledge;
- Motivational and moral component for successful professional activity;
- Specially designed practical training aimed at obtaining a specific qualification - technological training.

Research work was carried out on the basis of the following algorithm:

- Establishing a new integrated knowledge base based on basic knowledge in the field of "Human health";
- Identifying the profession of a pedagogue-psychologist working in the same or related field;
- Experimenting with a separate technological component included in the structure of practical activity of a pedagogue and psychologist;

- Creating a technological environment for customized training and additional education in the field of "kidnap management".

The task was carried out in the following sequence:

1. To study the social purchase of the society to a specialist with certain knowledge and qualifications;
2. Approbation of a separate technological component in a specialist with specialized education;
3. To study the practice of practical training of a group of experts of Foreign and Uzbek scientists;
4. Development and approbation of a start-up technological plan on the basis of TSPU;
5. Analysis of the obtained results and development of methodical recommendations.

The methodology of V. Simonov, Yu. Dement'eva "Methodology for assessing the adaptability and adaptability of a person to pedagogical activity" (adapted by N.S. Safoyev, D.S. Karshiyeva) was chosen for our diagnostic work, which is limited to determining the psychological characteristics of the teacher-psychologist's adaptation to professional activity. This methodology is focused on the study of the characteristics of the teacher's attitude to creativity, ability to work, ability to cope, communicativeness, adaptation, confidence in one's own strength, level of self-control.

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